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Opinion piece:

Trusting science in a day and age when misinformation is rife

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The scientific peer-review system is the trusted method for the evaluation of original research prior to publication. Although peer-review does at rare occasions fail to detect misconduct, in general, it is the accepted method for determining whether research contains trustworthy information. In addition to the peer-review system, nowadays publication in reputed journals also requires that the raw data and results are publicized on open-source platforms and/or repositories to which everyone has access. This allows readers to decide if the data presented are valid and interpreted accurately. This requirement has been a huge step forward regarding the reliability and integrity of scientific information and research in general.

More recently, preprint servers such as biorxiv.org, have gained popularity as a means to disseminate research findings quickly and prior to traditional peer-review, which can be time consuming, in particular for publication in high-end journals. This trend has been tremendously helpful in accelerating science and has made research results more accessible as the servers are not behind a paywall, and has thus allowed for transparent, community-driven peer-review, independent of traditional publishers. It does, however, not have the quality control measures in place as required by traditional publishers, such as making reported data and results freely available prior to release. The sole threshold for publication on biorxiv.org, for example, is that all authors agree to the publication. The platform clearly states that the deposition of the preprints occurs without any peer-review beyond a basic assessment for plagiarism and 'offensive, dangerous, and/or non-scientific content'. Thus, ill-meaning authors are able to disseminate misleading information and can potentially abuse this well-meant policy.

On 9th of January 2023, a paper was published on the biorxiv.org platform (<https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2023.01.08.522890v1>) claiming breakthrough results for the electron microscopy community, while acknowledging several researchers as contributing to the information presented in the article. The community immediately commented on the low scientific rigor of this work and the apparent lack of publicly deposited data in standard community repositories such as Electron Microscopy Data Bank (EMDB) or Protein Data Bank (PDB).

Additionally, some scientists raised doubts regarding the supposed affiliation of the author and contacted the researchers mentioned in the acknowledgement regarding the validity of the results.

Biorxiv.org was immediately contacted by the scientists mentioned in the acknowledgements who distanced themselves from the publication noting three things: Firstly, that the author was no longer a member of the supposedly affiliated institution, thus not entitled to use the affiliation; secondly, that researchers mentioned in the acknowledgements did not carry out tasks described therein; thirdly, a scientific justification explaining why the results were, in their view, impossible was expounded. Biorxiv.org acknowledged that they took these complaints very seriously but stated that they could not take sides and did not have the resources to carry out an investigation. A post that was submitted outlining the points above was however not published as it did not comply with the community guidelines and only the scientific part (point 3) was considered publishable according to the rules. The points regarding fraud of institutional affiliation and mis-assignment of tasks to researchers making them apparently complicit in a fraudulent research was not considered publishable according to current rules. Biorxiv.org's sole action was in contacting the author, but they refused to publish a formal commentary from the scientists concerned in response to the article, noting the site's comment moderation policies.

Only after an email from the institution's president indicating the possibility of legal action, the article was marked to be withdrawn by biorxiv.org.

In our opinion, this unfortunate incident has done well to show the strengths and weaknesses of the biorxiv.org platform and pre-print servers in general. High-quality, independent peer-review of the scientific content of this article was available to the community almost immediately by means of online discussions. Importantly, it was sobering for us to realize that through affiliation, a non-established scientist gained enormous credibility in the research community even though the claims in the publication do not even stand initial quality checks. Clarification about other important aspects, however, such as supposed affiliation, supposed contributions and scientific misconduct remained hidden from public eye up until withdrawal. Policies and detailed procedures of biorxiv.org regarding scientific misconduct and comment moderation are opaque to many, as evident in private and public discussions about the article.

Much effort has been undertaken in the last decades to preserve the reliability and reproducibility of science communication, as well as making data and articles accessible. We believe, that like the increasingly stringent publication policies of journals, additional standards will also need to be implemented for pre-print publishing to guarantee high quality standards, the reproducibility of data and avoiding publication of fraudulent reports in the future. Policies and procedures regarding misconduct allegations should be made transparent and should be taken more seriously. Researchers and institutions acknowledged in a scientific work should be asked to give informed consent prior to publication. As the importance of pre-print publications as a primary communication tool is constantly increasing, these issues are highly relevant to preserve good scientific standards.